

COLORATIVE MECHANISM STUDY OF CELADON GLAZE BY MÖSSBAUER SPECTROSCOPY

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1. Introduction

What highlights the excellence of formative characteristics and inlaying techniques of Goryeo celadon is the unique color whose artistic value is recognized worldwide.[1] Gangjin, which is a small town in the southern part of Korea, is known for celadon since Goryeo Dynasty (A.D. 918~1392). The celadon glaze was developed and refined during the 10th and 11th centuries in that area. Systematic studies for the reproduction of celadon in various areas such as glazes and clay based bodies are currently being conducted.

The color of Goryeo celadon is developed through the formation of glassy and crystalline phases, which are generated by the physical and chemical reactions between glaze and clay based body during the reduction firing process at high temperature. Glaze is generally composed of feldspar, lime stone, and clay minerals. Feldspar used as a flux material helps form glassy phase, and small amount of Fe ion acts as a color former in the glass. The color and glossness of celadon are significantly influenced by the Fe ions.

In this study, relationship between the electronic structure of Fe and the chromaticity of the celadon glaze was investigated by Mössbauer spectroscopy. The values of L*, a*, and b* in CIE space was measured for the celadon glaze and the relationship between the electronic states of Fe and the chromaticity was quantitatively studied.

2. Experimental

The composition of coloring element of Fe₂O₃, TiO₂, MnO, and P₂O₅ was varied was shown in Table 1. The basic glaze and the coloring element was mixed in pot mill for 24 hrs with the dispersant (1% cerasperse). In this work, whiteware body was used to minimize the effect of Fe in body on the

chromaticity of the glaze. The glaze was sprayed on whiteware specimens(50mm×50mm) calcined at 900 °C and then reductively sintered at 1260 °C. When temperature of electrical furnace reach 900 °C, the mixed gas of air and LPG(5/0.7 L/min) was used to induce reductive atmosphere. After sintering, CIE L*, a*, and b* values were measured by Cary 100 UV-Visible Spectrophotometer and analyzed by KS tone.

Table 1. Composition of coloring oxide added to basic glaze

No	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	MnO	P ₂ O ₅
2	1.40	1.00	0.80	0.30
13	2.20	0.10	0.20	0.30
18	2.20	0.10	0.20	1.60
25	2.20	1.00	0.80	0.30
29	2.20	1.00	0.80	0.30
34	1.40	0.1	0.20	0.30

3. Results and Discussion

The range of Fe₂O₃, TiO₂, MnO, P₂O₅ was selected in the values obtained from Goryeo celadon from Gangjin. Accordingly, the level of solid content was fixed to be 1.4/2.2 % for Fe₂O₃, 0.1/1.0% for TiO₂, 0.2/0.8% for MnO, 0.3/1.3% for P₂O₅, respectively. The measured CIE L*, a*, and b* values are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Mössbauer analysis results

No.	L*	a*	b*	Fe ³⁺ (line)		Fe ²⁺ (Doublet)1		Area (%)
				Δ (mm/s)	Area (%)	ΔEQ (mm/s)	δ (mm/s)	
34	78.14	-8.63	2.09	0.0965	5.74	1.8593	0.9056	94.26
13	74.59	-10.3	2.82	0.1972	7.76	1.9253	0.9015	92.33
2	70.63	-3.02	21.92	0.0968	8.22	1.8651	0.9383	91.78
18	69.62	-10	7.84	-0.0565	9.85	1.8387	0.9343	90.15
25	61.23	-2.34	33.77	0.0081	14.32	1.8151	0.9323	85.68
29	48.7	10.15	45.38	0.0965	18.06	1.9253	0.8726	81.94

The Mössbauer spectra were recorded with a fixed absorber and a moving source by using a conventional spectrometer of the electromechanical type. A ^{57}Co source in Rh matrix manufactured by Dupont was used at room temperature. To produce a uniform thickness over the area of the Mossbauer absorber, the amount of each sample were adjusted for ^{57}Fe density of $0.214 \text{ mg}/\text{Cm}^2$ and clamped between two beryllium disks with thickness of $0.005''$ and diameter of $1''$. Mössbauer spectra at room temperature were analyzed by two components with doublet and single line shape, which can be attributed to Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} , respectively, as shown in Table 2. All samples did not exhibit any magnetic behaviors at room temperature. The value of δ represents the isomer shift of Fe ion, and the *Area* indicates the relative area ratio of Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} , and ΔE_Q is the strength of the electric quadrupole interaction (electric quadrupole splitting).

Fig. 1. Evolution of L^* , a^* , and b^* values and wavelength at max. reflectance in UV spectra according to $\text{Fe}^{2+}/(\text{Fe}^{3+}+\text{Fe}^{2+})$ ratio

As show in Table 2, as the ratio of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} increases, the a^* and b^* values decrease. As shown in Fig. 1, as the ratio of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} increases, the peak position in UV-reflectance spectrum shifts toward low wavelength(high energy), which is well consistent with the coloring turn into BG as the a^* and b^* value decreases. As the ratio of Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} increases, the L^* value (brightness) increases.

For ancient Chinese Ru celadon,[2] the ratio of $\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ ranges from 64% to 79% and, as Fe^{2+} ion increases, peak position in UV spectrum decreases from 600nm to 420nm. The color changes from pea green, through powder green, to silky green. For

Yaozhou celadon, [3] the ratio of Fe^{2+} ranges from 55% to 75%, and as the ratio increases, the peak position decreases from 660nm to 550nm. The color changes from dark pea green, through pea green, to viridity. Accordingly, in Ru celadon and Yaozhou celadon, as the ratio Fe^{2+} to Fe^{3+} increases, the peak position decreases and coloring turns into BG with the increase of L^* value. This is well consistent with the fact that the sintering condition of Ru celadon with silky green is most reductive.

Fig. 2. Evolution of (a) L^* , (b) a^* , and (c) b^* values according to Fe^{2+} and Fe^{3+} area

4. Conclusion

Systematic study on relationship between celadon coloring and glaze component was conducted by chromaticity analysis and Mössbauer spectroscopic analysis. According to Mössbauer analysis results, as the amount of divalent iron ion increases, the a^* and b^* values decrease, on the other hand, L^* value increases. The ratio of divalent iron ion produced in reductive sintering process is found to be 80-95% in this study.

5. References

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